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**Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a
realistic solar-sail propelled CubeSat class
spacecraft targeting orbits around Mars and its
moons**

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Project Report
**Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a realistic
solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft
targeting orbits around Mars and its moons**

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List of Symbols

- Aerobraking** Aerobraking is a spaceflight technique that lowers an elliptical orbit's high point (apoapsis) by guiding the craft through the atmosphere at the orbit's low point (periapsis). As a result, the spaceship is slowed down. . 3, 11–14, 43, 64–67
- Aerocapture** Using aerodynamic drag force from a single pass through a planetary atmosphere, aerocapture is an orbital transfer technique that allows a spacecraft to decelerate and achieve orbit insertion.. 13, 23
- AOP** Argument of Perigee, The point on an orbital path when the satellite is closest to Mars.. 27, 67
- apogee** the point farthest from a planet or a satellite (such as the moon) reached by an object orbiting it. 3, 11, 13, 18, 26, 29, 31, 40, 53–55, 62, 63
- AU** An Astronomical Unit (AU) is the average distance between Earth and the Sun, which is about 150 million kilometers. Astronomical units are usually used to measure distances within our Solar System.. 32
- C3** C3 is the Characteristic energy needed to get into an orbit relative to the energy of an object with exactly the escape velocity. It is twice the specific energy (J/kg) and has units of velocity squared. A negative C3 indicates less than escape velocity (typically of Earth).. 18
- Darrel Conway** Founder and CEO of Thinking Systems(a company that provides GMAT services).. 9, 43
- Deimos** Deimos is the smaller and outermost of the two natural satellites of Mars, the other being Phobos. Deimos has a mean radius of 6.2 km and takes 30.3 hours to orbit Mars.. 10, 12, 19, 24, 26, 28, 30, 67
- ECC** Eccentricity, the distance between the foci of an ellipse divided by the major axis.. 27, 67
- epoch** Epoch is the moment in time used as a reference point for some time-varying astronomical quantity.. 27

- GMAT** The General Mission Analysis Tool is the only fully accessible, enterprise program available for designing, navigating, and optimizing space missions.. [4](#), [9–12](#), [19–21](#), [24–27](#), [31](#), [33–35](#), [37](#), [38](#), [43](#), [54](#), [57](#), [58](#), [63](#), [66–68](#)
- INC** Inclination, the angle between the equatorial plane and the orbital plane measured counter-clockwise at the ascending node.. [27](#), [67](#)
- JPL** Jet Propulsion Laboratory. [24](#)
- Jupyter Notebook** Project Jupyter is a project to develop open-source software, open standards, and services for interactive computing across multiple programming languages.. [63](#), [66](#)
- JupyterNotebook** It is a tool that may be used in a variety of industries and is the most recent web-based dynamic application software for algorithms and data.. [9](#)
- latitude** A celestial object’s angular distance north or south of the equator is often stated in degrees and minutes.. [16](#)
- LightSail 2** LightSail 2 is a project that demonstrates controlled solar travel in low Earth orbit using a CubeSat.. [21](#)
- longitude** A celestial object’s angular distance east or west of the equator is often stated in degrees and minutes.. [16](#)
- Mars** Mars is the fourth planet, Mars’s radius is second smallest among the planets in the Solar System at 3,389.5 km.. [3](#), [11–14](#), [16](#), [18](#), [19](#), [23](#), [24](#), [26–30](#), [35](#), [38](#), [39](#), [43](#), [53](#), [55](#), [58](#), [60](#), [61](#), [63–68](#)
- Mars Express** With its start of science activities in 2004, Mars Express has offered amazing three-dimensional pictures of Mars. It has produced the most comprehensive map of the atmosphere’s chemical composition, examined Phobos, Mars’s innermost moon, in previously unheard-of detail, and tracked the global water cycle, proving that Mars once supported potentially habitable environmental conditions for life.. [23](#)
- MOI** ”Mars Orbit insertion” was the point in the mission when Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter arrived just short of Mars, fired onboard rockets to slow its speed relative to the planet, and was captured into a long, looping orbit.. [17](#)
- MRO** The Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter.NASA’s Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter, known as MRO, is an orbiting spacecraft studying Mars’ climate and geology since 2006. Using the most powerful high-resolution camera ever sent

to Mars, MRO produces stunning images that help scientists discern how geologic forces shaped the surface.. [14](#), [17](#)

Oculus The Quest 2 is a virtual reality (VR) headset developed by Reality Labs, a division of Meta Platforms.. [4](#), [11](#), [35–38](#)

OFF Position It is the position in which the rotation of the Solar Sail changes and the photons coming from the Sun fall behind the sails.. [11](#)

ON Position Solar Sail’s sails reflect photons from the Sun.. [11](#)

perigee the point nearest a planet or a satellite (such as the moon) reached by an object orbiting it. [11](#), [13](#), [17](#), [18](#), [26](#), [29](#), [31](#), [40](#), [53](#), [54](#), [63](#)

Phobos Phobos is the innermost and larger of the two natural satellites of Mars, the other being Deimos. Phobos has a mean radius of 11 km and It orbits Mars much faster than Mars rotates and completes an orbit in just 7 hours and 39 minutes. [10](#), [12](#), [19](#), [24–26](#), [28](#), [30](#), [67](#)

RAAN Right ascension of the ascending node, the rotation of the orbit plane from the reference axis.. [27](#), [67](#)

RMAG Magnitude of the satellite’s position vector.. [29](#), [63](#)

SMA The semi-major axis (major semiaxis) is the longest semidiameter or one half of the major axis, and thus runs from the centre, through a focus, and to the perimeter.. [27](#), [55](#), [60](#), [67](#)

solar-sail Solar sails are a type of spacecraft propulsion system that makes use of the radiation pressure imposed by sunlight on wide mirrors.. [11](#), [12](#), [21](#), [55](#), [57–60](#), [64](#), [68](#)

SRP Solar Radiation Pressure. The pressure on a surface resulting from electromagnetic radiation that impinges on it, which results from the momentum carried by that radiation; radiation pressure is doubled if the radiation is reflected rather than absorbed. [11](#), [12](#), [16](#), [19](#), [26](#), [29](#), [31](#), [33](#), [34](#), [53](#)

STK Systems Tool Kit, or STK, is a similar system to ViDI. It is a piece of 3D physics-based modeling software from Ansys Government Initiatives (AGI), and can help simulate virtual versions of real-life missions.. [21](#)

TA True Anomaly, angle in the orbit plane between the perihelion point and the position of the orbiting object.. [27](#), [67](#)

VR Virtual reality (VR) is a simulated experience that employs pose tracking and 3D near-eye displays to give the user an immersive feel of a virtual world..
[3](#), [4](#), [35](#), [37](#), [67](#)

WolframLanguage It is a metaphorical language that was purposefully created with the depth and coherence required to create effective programs rapidly..
[9](#)

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We express our gratitude to Fabrizio Pinto for his strong support throughout the writing process of our thesis. We also thank the creators of the Free Wolfram Engine for the [WolframLanguage](#) language for providing this valuable resource to [JupyterNotebook](#) users. Special thanks to [Darrel Conway](#) (NASA [GMAT](#) developer) for helping us with the exponential Martian atmosphere. Thanks are due to Dr. Ravishankar Mathur for his help with the OpenFrames Interface. Finally, we thank Mr. Jay Trimble (NASA Ames), Mission System Manager of the VIPER Lunar Rover, who provided initial comments and a helpful critique of our results.

Abstract

Solar sailing is a cutting-edge technique for propelling a spacecraft across space. It is particularly important, especially when compared to modern, traditional spacecraft, in terms of its fuel efficiency. Most spacecraft rely on chemical rockets to alter their trajectory or accelerate once they have been launched from Earth. These rockets burn fuel that is carried onboard the spacecraft. Nevertheless, the act of carrying additional rocket fuel results in an augmented mass. Once spacecraft achieve their maximum velocity, they typically continue moving through space without propulsion or rely on the gravitational force of other planets to get to their destination. A spacecraft equipped with solar sails can achieve perpetual acceleration as long as it is subjected to the force of light. Solar radiation exerts a force on the sail of a spaceship within a solar system, causing it to accelerate during the duration of the mission. It indicates that spacecraft propelled by solar sails can achieve velocities that chemical rockets cannot match. This study will facilitate the advancement of the initiative to launch a CubeSat spacecraft propelled by solar sails to Mars. To ensure utmost precision in the mission, a comprehensive orbital study of various Mars orbiter missions is conducted. The resulting trajectories, as well as the orbits of Mars's moons, [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#), are incorporated into the script. Furthermore, the necessary orbital design and analysis are conducted to facilitate travel around [glsMars](#) and its moons. The findings of this study showcased the advantages of solar sailing and the possibility of doing interplanetary journeys without the need for chemical engines. This work employs the cannonball model to simulate solar radiation pressure with enhanced accuracy. The objective was to develop a more dependable simulation model utilizing data supplied by NASA. The utilization of virtual reality glasses improved the simulation model. Moreover, many complementary and publicly available software packages such as [GMAT](#), Horizons, and Mathematica are employed for in-depth talks on analysis, graphing, and simulations. The objective of this study is to function as a guide for future interplanetary solar sail expeditions.

1 Introduction

Spacecraft are developing rapidly due to the increasing interest of science in exploring the depths of space, especially [Mars](#), in the last century and humanity's desire to travel back in time. On the contrary, solar sailing has improved over conventional spacecraft in terms of affordability, accessibility, and low fuel consumption. Additionally, due to the intensive use of CubeSats, costs are further reduced. The average amount of fuel consumed on a spacecraft intended to be used for the survival of human society in Mars orbit is approximately seven tonnes. Fuel will be needed regularly during the process of establishing a settlement on Mars, and transporting this fuel need from Earth when conventional space vehicles are used can be described as high cost and a waste of time [1]. Solar Sails provide the energy needed to move through space by reflecting photons from their large mirror-like lightweight sails. Solar sails produce the energy needed to travel through space by reflecting photons from their lightweight, mirror-like sails. Momentum transfer occurs when solar photons hit the membrane; this flow is defined by the Solar Radiation Pressure ([SRP](#)). [2] The goal of this research, through NASA's [GMAT](#) program, is to design a Solar Sail vehicle with six orbital elements, mass, and SRP area that eliminates limited resource fuel consumption by using solar energy.

The objective is to achieve progress by focusing on the goal of [Aerobraking](#) the orbit of [Mars](#) through the utilization of solar photons to propel the 40 kg [solar-sail](#). According to NASA, the simulation was conducted using the open-source NASA [GMAT](#) software. The SPAD file was imported during the simulation process. However, the method of adding a drawing model of an existing spacecraft was not utilized. The acquired values were juxtaposed with the outcomes computed using Jupyter to verify the precision of the simulation. Consequently, its precision was verified. In the current study, NASA conducted a simulation using GMAT to define [solar-sail](#) as a cannonball. The simulation was carried out without including the SPAD file. Additionally, virtual reality glasses ([Oculus 2](#)) were used to enhance realism and improve the simulation based on the data obtained, aligning it with the evolving global context.

Building upon the previous thesis [3] and advancing the concept of the Solar Sail, the objective of achieving successful aerobraking into [Mars](#)' atmosphere has been accomplished. By incorporating the Martian atmosphere into NASA [GMAT](#), the photons emitted by the Sun have effectively penetrated the atmosphere of Mars after bouncing off the Solar Sail's sails and propelling the spacecraft. Through the manipulation of the [ON Position/OFF Position](#), the [perigee](#) decreases while the [apogee](#) increases, ultimately reaching the minimum measurable distance. After

traversing a distance of 60,406 kilometers and maintaining its orbit around [Mars](#), the periapsis of the [solar-sail](#) falls while the apoapsis grows. As a result, the [solar-sail](#) travels away from [Mars](#) and successfully completes its [Aerobraking](#) maneuver to enter [Mars](#)' orbit.

As authors of this thesis, we would like to mention that this trajectory design thesis is just a part of the whole mission. Therefore, we would like to thank to other authors of this mission for writing the thesis for different aspects of the mission. Kiymet Yildir, who is the author of "Autonomous optical and inertial navigation of a realistic solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting orbits around Mars and its moons" [4] and also Dogukan Coskun, Hayriye Memis, Elif Gokyolcu, who are the authors of "Proof-of-concept of a realistic solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft digital twin targeting orbits around Mars and its moons". We are grateful for their contribution for this Mars mission. [5]

1.1 Problem Statment

The aim of this study is to expand on and advance the previous research titled "Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting [Mars](#) and its moons within the context of the intended objective. To provide more realistic results, the three Mars orbiters (MEX, MAVEN, and Mars Odyssey), as well as [Mars](#)' moons [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#), are manually defined into the algorithm. This advancement enabled the mission to potentially include flybys of Mars' moons. The trajectories of the three spacecraft orbiting [Mars](#) are examined, and the primary spacecraft's orbit has been modified as needed to avoid collisions. Thus, the target is to place the Martian into its orbit by aerobraking the CubeSat, then slow down and descend. [3]

1.2 Motivation

The motivation for this research derives from the rapid advancements in spacecraft development and the increasing fascination with exploring remote solar systems, namely [Mars](#). Solar sailing shows promise as a viable method for surpassing these limitations. Solar sailing has several advantages over conventional spacecraft in terms of cost, availability, and decreased fuel use. Solar sails offer a propulsion mechanism that eliminates the requirement for significant fuel reserves by harnessing the energy from sunlight using their large, reflective, and lightweight sails. The researchers want to develop a solar sail vehicle with precise specifications, including six orbital elements, mass, and the area affected by solar radiation pressure (SRPt), using NASA's [GMAT](#) software. The primary objective of this research is to explore more sustainable and economically efficient propeller tech-

niques in spacecraft design, with a specific focus on the viability of solar sailing for interplanetary missions, particularly those targeted toward [Mars](#).

1.3 [Aerobraking](#)

Aerobraking is the process by which an object approaching a planet or other body with an atmosphere slows down due to atmospheric drag. Alternatively referred to as atmospheric breaking, it is a purposeful technique that can be used in circumstances in which there is sufficient atmosphere to change a spacecraft's orbit or slow a vehicle down before landing. To achieve this, the high-orbiting spacecraft propels itself into an elliptical orbit with a [perigee](#) (lowest point) inside the atmosphere. At [perigee](#), air drag lowers velocity, lowering the [apogee](#), or the highest point of the orbit. A propulsive burn is made at [apogee](#) after one or more passes through the atmosphere, lowering the apoapsis to the desired altitude. As a consequence, the orbit becomes circular, the periapsis increases out of the atmosphere. [6]

[Aerocapture](#) is: An orbit insertion maneuver is known as [Aerocapture](#). When a spacecraft reaches a planet on a hyperbolic trajectory for the first time, it passes through its atmosphere once before slowing down and entering a captured orbit. [Aerobraking](#) and direct propulsive orbit insertion are regarded as complementary approaches to [Aerocapture](#) on Mars. [7]

1.3.1 [Aerobraking At Mars](#)

The spacecraft enters the planet's upper atmosphere, slows down due to increased friction, and descends as its elliptical orbit changes to a circular one. At the bottom of the circulation with the elliptical Mars center point, kinetic energy is at its maximum and potential energy is at its minimum. This is the [perigee](#) moment. At the top of circulation, at the point where it is farthest from the center of Mars, there is no speed, and the maximum potential energy becomes the minimum kinetic energy. This is the moment of apoapsis. Potential and kinetic energy can never be zero in a spacecraft. To reduce the distance of the spacecraft from the center of the red planet, the [apogee](#) height is reduced by reducing the kinetic energy. The spacecraft can be managed to alter the [perigee](#)'s altitude and hence adjust the amount of aerobraking that takes place during the orbit by firing thrusters at the apoapsis. Exact control over the spacecraft's trajectory and its contact with the Martian atmosphere is made possible by this method, which is essential for maximizing scientific discoveries or guaranteeing a safe landing. [8]

2 Literature Survey

2.1 Andrew J Tang and Xiaofeng Wu, et al. "An Interplanetary Mission Design of a Solar Sailing CubeSat to Mars" (2020)

Orbital solar sailing missions are rare, despite the fact that solar sailing missions have been developed in the past. Making the most of solar sailing spacecraft has the potential to increase access to the solar system. An analysis of a controlled solar sailing trip to Mars with a CubeSat platform is conducted as part of a feasibility assessment. There will be two phases to this expedition, which will analyze the trajectory optimization of several sail architectures launched from Earth. It will also be examined how well solar sailing spacecraft accomplish aerobraking capture, because this is currently a major obstacle to their ability to travel interplanetary distances without using chemical propulsion to enter orbit.

Similar aerobraking maneuvers were used by the Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO) to create a polar Martian orbit, with the spacecraft descending to as low as 93 km during progressive orbital [Aerobraking](#). Therefore, 100 km above the Martian surface was the minimum permissible altitude for aerobraking as a reference guideline. In order to replicate near-zero and low HEV, two distinct hyperbolic excess velocities, 100 m/s and 2000 m/s, were investigated. Spacecraft that have drag regions of 50 m² or more are good candidates for aerobraking. These spacecrafts have hourly orbital durations that can be rapidly extended into the appropriate Martian orbit by sustained aerobraking. It is important to emphasize that while larger surface area spacecraft can approach the planet at an angle to lessen [Aerobraking](#), the contrary cannot happen. Therefore, aerobraking capture is perfectly feasible for our solar sailing concepts, wherein the spacecraft may be maneuvered to rearrange its orbit by utilizing the pressure forces of solar radiation at [Mars](#). [9]

Figure 1: Figure of the mission

[9]

2.2 Edoardo Fornari , Mauro Pontani et al.”Mars orbit injection via aerocapture and low-thrust nonlinear orbit control”

[10]

Previous Mars missions have employed a variety of orbit injection procedures, including as prolonged, repeated aerobraking passes, with the goal of determining the optimal operational orbit. Planetary aerobraking is the result of multiple atmospheric passes that lower the initial elliptic orbit’s semimajor axis and eccentricity around the target planet. It was looked at and carried out in relation to the Mars Reconnaissance, Mars Odyssey, and Mars Global Surveyor missions. A different method is called planetary aerocapture, and it involves making a single atmospheric pass to lower a spacecraft’s hyperbolic velocity to a value that corresponds to an elliptic orbit upon arrival at the planet. Astrodynamics has been quite interested in this type of maneuver since the 1960s.

2.2.1 Solar Radiation Pressure

The solar radiation pressure (**SRP**), which results from photons interacting with the spacecraft in the presence of light, is related to an additional disruptive acceleration. The cannonball concept is used for simplicity, and the affecting acceleration based on by solar radiation is

$$\mathbf{a}^{(SR)} = -vP_{SR} \frac{c_R S_R}{m} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_S \quad (1)$$

where c_R , is a measure of the radiative coefficient connected to the type of radiation contact with the spacecraft, and P_{SR} , is the solar radiation pressure **SRP** at Mars, The activated spacecraft cross section is symbolized by S_R , the shadow function is symbolized by v , and the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_S$ is the one that lines up with the Sun position vector $\mathbf{a}$ (obtained from the center of **Mars**).

2.2.2 Model Of Mars Atmosphere

When compared to Earth’s atmosphere, the Martian atmosphere is extremely rare. Accurate atmospheric density models is required to investigate aerocapture. Using data on Martian atmospheric density that varies on (a) altitude h , (b) geographical longitude λ g, (c) latitude γ , and (d) climatic scenario, this analysis makes use of

the Mars Climate Database (MCD). The second category covers all potential meteorological and seasonal conditions on Mars that are influenced by solar activity and depend on the true anomaly of Mars along its orbit. Consequently, there are significant changes in the dust concentration, which significantly impacts the air density.

The climatology model was determined to be the accepted model based on prior research and computer simulations, as well as historical data about dust distribution. Rather, the cold-scenario model predicts a highly pure environment with very low dust density numbers and minimal solar activity. Conversely, the warm-scenario model takes into account high dust density and maximum solar activity values. Lastly, the dust-storm-scenario model relates to the maximum densities and implies that storms happen on the entire planet. Additionally, the air density is generally higher in close proximity to the equator. Thus, it is possible to assume that the air density depends entirely on altitude and not on particular atmospheric conditions. This idea is used moving forward. [10]

2.3 Dr. Daniel T. Lyons et al.”MARS RECONNAISSANCE ORBITER: AEROBRAKING REFERENCE TRAJECTORY”

[11]

During the 2005 Mars launch chance, the Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter spacecraft will be launched on an intermediate class, consumable launch vehicle on a Type 1 trajectory between August 8 and August 28. Following the spacecraft’s propellant capture into a 35-hour highly elliptical orbit with a 300 km [perigee](#) altitude, the test phase will be followed by a 6-month aerobraking phase.

The irregularity of atmospheric density changes makes aerobraking the most risky. Unacceptable dangerous temperatures on open spacecraft areas, particularly the solar panels and the high-gain antennas, might occur from an unexpected rise in density. Spreading the aerobraking phase evenly over the six months available for the mean local solar time change will optimize the leeway for handling the atmospheric instability. With so much time to use aerobraking and a comparatively low spacecraft ballistic factor, [MRO](#) will have greater leeway than any other aerobraking goal to adjust to atmospheric variability. For Mars Orbit Insertion ([MOI](#)), the periapsis height goal has to be set high enough above the atmosphere to account for navigational mistakes made along the journey to Mars. A target with a periapsis of 300 km offers a sensible ratio between security and propelling productivity during the pushing transfer into orbit upon landing. In the unlikely event that a Deep Space Network (DSN) issue prohibits timely spacecraft controlling, the southern approach lowers risk due to its ideal attribute of periapsis tending

to move outside of the atmosphere for the majority of the aerobraking period. In the aerobraking stage, the inclination varies by a very small amount, therefore the capture orbit will be aimed very near the ideal final level. The approach path, which mostly depends on the launch and arrival dates—which were selected to guarantee a fixed mean local solar time upon arrival—determines the node. This approach almost reduces the sum of the arrival V-infinity and the launch C_3 (The launch energy, C_3 , is defined as the square of the hyperbolic excess velocity. V_∞ of the spacecraft with respect to the Earth, a measure related to how much velocity increase must be supplied to the spacecraft by the launch vehicle at launch). The best course of action is to choose a date that minimizes the delta-V needed to capture into orbit and accept the resulting node as a starting point, even though the node can be somewhat altered by adjusting the date of its arrival. A sequence of propelling "walk-in" actions at apogee reduces the periapsis height from the starting 300 km perigee height, causing aerobraking. The initial movement reduces perigee to around 150 kilometers in height. The perigee is lowered by several additional, gradually smaller movements on subsequent orbits until the required dynamic pressure for aerobraking is reached. The initial maneuver is to reach a height where damages cannot occur even in the densest possible environment, but where drag should be noticeable in a less dense atmosphere. The remaining walk-in maneuvers for the real mission will be calculated using the density values measured in the earlier orbits. [11]

2.4 Bruno V. Sarli, Ariadna Farres, David C. Folta et al."Mars Optimal Aerobrake Maneuver Estimation"

[12]

Mars research satellites frequently alter their orbits to gain data, ground tracking, or relay functions. Air resistance, often known as the aerobrake, can reduce semi-major axis and eccentricity. The preparation and execution of aerobraking is one of the trickiest planetary orbit maneuvers. The primary goal of aerobraking is to keep the spacecraft's perigee within a designated air-density corridor. This is achieved by making one or more quick, tiny adjustments to raise or lower perigee. Propeller limitations force these maneuvers to be executed as efficiently as feasible. Aerobraking is the process of affecting a spacecraft's orbit by utilizing strongly atmospheric drag in conjunction with attitude control system maneuvers. The atmospheric brake is typically employed in place of propellant to reduce apogee. Designing for aerobrake movements are difficult for different causes. From the point of view of flight dynamics, the requirement to precisely account for orbital perturbations is arguably the most significant. To forecast how the spacecraft's orbit will evolve, higher-order gravitational perturbations, perturbing gravitating

third bodies, and atmospheric drag must all be taken into consideration, especially for Martian missions. Furthermore, adding drag effects necessitates taking into account the spacecraft's attitude as well as the dynamics of the Martian atmosphere, which significantly increases the problem's modeling complexity. The primary factors influencing a satellite's motion must be taken seriously while modeling the dynamics of a satellite orbiting Mars. This article examines the following topics: the solar radiation pressure (SRP) using the cannonball model (spacecraft attitude evaluation is outside the focus of this work); the atmosphere's drag using Mars GRAM-2005; the gravity field of Mars using the Mars-50C harmonics up to degree and order 50; and the point mass gravity perturbations from the Sun, Jupiter, Phobos, and Deimos. The General Mission Analysis Tool is used for condition propagation (GMAT). GMAT is a free software program created at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center for space mission design and operation. The software facilitates the creation of mission regimes and trajectory optimization for a variety of applications, including deep space missions, interplanetary travel, low-Earth orbit, and moon operations. The ability to generate the STM through the propagation of the variational equations and the simple, dynamic calculation of trajectories around Mars using high-fidelity force simulations are two of this tool's features that are particularly relevant in this context. By employing a high-fidelity model for the STM's propagation, it is possible to map the area surrounding a reference orbit while accurately capturing the previously mentioned second-order effects. [12]

2.5 Darrel J. Conway, Steven P. Hughes, et al. "The General Mission Analysis Tool (GMAT): Current Features And Adding Custom Functionality"(2010)

[13]

NASA, the Air Force Research Lab, and the private sector created the General Mission Analysis Tool ([GMAT](#)), a software program for path estimation, mission analysis, trajectory estimate, and forecasting the cases. The design and operation of the [GMAT](#) are predicated on four fundamental ideas: visibility of open sources for both user extensibility, modular design, platform freedom, source code and design documentation. Due to the architecture of [GMAT](#), the engine's components operate on objects via rather abstract classes to imitate spaceship missions. It is possible to design objects that specialize these abstract interfaces into specific spaceship simulation elements by specializing in these classes. To put it another way, GMAT simulates a spacecraft mission by breaking down high-level classes into smaller classes that are in charge of orbital computations, numerical simulation of the spacecraft and its surroundings, and the chronology that outlines the evolution of these components. The architectural elements that a user perceives as resources and commands are these specialized subclasses. Trajectories may be shown in space, parameters can be plotted against each other, and parameters can be saved to files for processing at a later time. Users may zoom in on specific locations of interest and plot data while a mission is being executed thanks to the fully interactive trajectory and plot features. GMAT enables users to rotate the view and change attention to any item in the display. Trajectories and data may be seen in any coordinate system that is defined in GMAT. Users can follow the trajectory's progress over time by animating the trajectory view. [13]

2.6 David A. Spencer, et al.”The LightSail 2 solar sailing technology demonstration”(2021)

[14]

The Planetary Society has been funding solar sailing technology for ten years, and the LightSail 2 mission is the result of that effort. LightSail 2’s goal is to use a CubeSat platform to demonstrate controlled solar sailing in Earth orbit. There are two flying missions in the LightSail program. On May 20, 2015, LightSail 1 was launched as a component of the ULTRASat payload and placed into an elliptical orbit measuring 356 km by 705 km with a 55 degree inclination. The only goals of the LightSail 1 mission were to validate the solar sail deployment procedure and check in on CubeSat operation while in orbit. On June 7, 2015, the LightSail 1 [solar-sail](#) was successfully deployed after 18 days of on-orbit checkout and anomaly response procedures. The LightSail program’s objectives have been completed by LightSail 2. LightSail 2’s demonstration of controlled solar sailing on a CubeSat platform has made significant progress the field of solar sailing technology. By adjusting the position of the solar sail with respect to the Sun, LightSail 2 seeks to demonstrate solar sail propulsion. Twice every orbit, the sail control algorithm alternates the sail orientation between pushing and edge-on positions by means of a cycle of ”On-Off” slews about the Y axis of the spacecraft. The evolution of the [LightSail 2](#) orbital state shows the impacts of solar pressure. After sail deployment and the start of sail control, the orbit’s apogee progressively climbed, and as the orbit grew more eccentric, the perigee altitude fell. July 31, 2019 was the date on which The Planetary Society pronounced [LightSail 2](#) mission successful. This was based on the reconstruction of attitude history demonstrating appropriate sail control and the subsequent orbit development from TLE data. [14]

2.7 Ravishankar Mathur ,et al.”VISUAL INTERACTIVE TRAJECTORY DESIGN”(2015)

[15]

Over the last twenty years, astrodynamics applications have advanced to the point where high-fidelity visualizations are now standard equipment for mission design and analysis, rather than being unique or optional. commonly used commercial and governmental instruments, including Systems Tool Kit ([STK](#)).

The General Mission Analysis Tool ([GMAT](#)), Copernicus2, and ([STK](#)) all have 3D visualizations that offer vital information well above and beyond what text-based data or static graphs can. These days, effective trajectory design and optimization depend heavily on these visualizations; in fact, they are now used to influence

design choices rather than only being used to provide images and presentations.

Through research and development, a novel application of visual analytics known as Visual Interactive Trajectory Design (VITD) is presented in this paper. It enables the user to efficiently "grab and drag" spacecraft and instantly see how changes in state affect the spacecraft's trajectory.

It is crucial to remember that VITD is not intended to replace conventional means of teaching orbital mechanics or sophisticated methods of trajectory design, such as machine learning algorithms, initial guess generators, and mathematical analyses. Instead, it is a tool that supports these efforts by offering a fresh interactive method of adjusting design parameters that makes better use of the user's innate ability to process and analyze visual information.

2.8 Karl B. Hille, et al."Better than Reality"(2020)

[16]

Many are familiar with virtual reality (VR) to experience out-of-this-world video gaming, but few may be aware that it can be used to make scientific discoveries. Using a customized, Goddard-developed 3-D simulation that animated the speed and direction of four million stars in the local Milky Way neighborhood, Goddard astronomer Marc Kuchner and researcher Susan Higashio obtained a new perspective on their motions, which helped them classify star groupings.

NASA already has ambitious plans to use lasers to transport gigabytes of data, but these plans have only been limited to near-Earth or larger deep-space missions thus far.

A newly developed device that might act as an early-warning system for astronauts in case of damaging radiation and a planned small-satellite mission aimed at demonstrating miniaturized optical communications technology that can handle enormous data rates from deep space could change that.

Grubb demonstrated how an engineer might "draw" the cable path through the instruments and other components in a Restore-L spacecraft mockup, for example, and the software could show the cable length to follow that path. Hardware assembly, maintenance, and repair tool paths can also be virtually designed.

2.9 ESA, et al.”ESA explores bold new approach to Mars orbit”(2023)

[17]

On Christmas Day 2003, [Mars Express](#) reached the Red Planet at a speed of 18,000 km/h. In order to slow down sufficiently to be brought into orbit and prevent it from taking off into space, it had to fire its main engine. Although the braking was successful, 264 kg of propellant were utilized. Since 1971, this method has been successfully applied on 16 missions to Mars, including the 2016 Trace Gas Orbiter mission from ESA. What would happen if we piloted a spaceship directly through [Mars](#)’ atmosphere, using atmospheric drag instead of propellant to slow it down? ’[Aerocapture](#)’ is not an entirely new concept. Since the middle of the 1960s, engineers have been drawn to it for two main reasons. First off, it would require less propellant to be carried by the spacecraft. Secondly, it would imply that we may opt to reach a planet faster, reducing the duration of our cruise. [Aerocapture](#) has the potential to propel tiny spacecraft into orbit and, in the future, to benefit larger spacecraft involved in human exploration missions. Although [Mars](#) is a desirable starting point for applying aerocapture outside of Earth, the benefits of the technology are most noticeable for large-scale scientific missions to planets with atmospheres larger than Jupiter. However, [Aerocapture](#) has never been tried—on Mars or any other planet. Until now, the concept has been deemed too dangerous for its initial application in a scientific mission, and it has been deemed too costly to send a spacecraft to Mars just to demonstrate [Aerocapture](#). One of the main issues with [Aerocapture](#) is control. You are, quite literally, in control of the spacecraft when you use thrusters to slow it down. However, in order to get the spacecraft in the required orbit, [Aerocapture](#) requires precisely the correct amount of atmospheric drag. The spacecraft’s dimensions, shape, velocity, angle of entry, and Mars’s atmosphere all affect drag. Every research looked at two different kinds of missions: one that was ’piggybacking’ on an existing [Mars](#) mission and the other that was freestanding. The ArianeGroup team looked on inflatable drag devices with a rigid center shell for both kinds. For the solo trip, the Vorticity team looked into an alternative inflatable decelerator; for the piggyback mission, they aimed for a concept that relied as much as possible on current technology, utilizing solely rigid drag devices.

3 Methodology

For a realistic mission, as many celestial objects should be added into the [GMAT](#) simulation. For this purpose, [Mars](#) moons, [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#) will be added:

3.0.1 Adding Phobos

Inside GMAT, we find “Solar System” under resource tree. Right click [Mars](#), and click “add” and “Moon”. Here we type the name of the moon. After doing this we open the moon’s properties. Following values will be needed:

Mu : $0.00070934 \text{ km}^3/\text{sec}^2$

Equatorial Radius : 13.5 km

Flattening : 0.3185185185185186

Figure 2: Phobos Properties

Under the “Orbit” tab we write the NAIF ID part “401”. This is the international identification number for [Phobos](#). Then we put the “mar085.bsp” file into the SPK files part. This is the ephemeris file for [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#) which you can download on [JPL](#)’s planetary data system. [18]

Figure 3: Phobos Orbit Properties

3.0.2 Adding Deimos

Adding Deimos into [GMAT](#) is the same as adding [Phobos](#). But we use the following values this time:

Mu : $0.000158817 \text{ km}^3/\text{sec}^2$

Equatorial Radius : 7.5 km

Flattening : 0.3066666666666666

NAIF ID : 402

3.0.3 Adding Propagator

After adding Mars's moons, we must add a propagator for the simulation. We are mainly going to have 3 propagators. One of these propagators will have solar radiation pressure activated and the other one will not use that. When we tell GMAT to use these two propagators back to back, it is going to act as if there are SRP at apoapsis and there is no SRP in perigee. We right-click "Propagators" under the resource tree and add propagator. In the force model, we choose the Sun as the central body. We add everything besides Phobos, Deimos and Mars into the point masses. We enable Solar Radiation Pressure for the propagator that we are going to use as apogee. The third propagator will be used to tell the program to stop the simulation based on the elapsed seconds.

Figure 4: Propagator Set Up to Apogee

3.0.4 Adding New Coordinate System

As default, GMAT opens with Earth based coordinate system. Therefore, we would like to have Sun-based coordinates. This part is crucial for designing the spacecraft behaviors. Under the resource tree, we right-click coordinate systems and click "add new coordinate system". Here we select the origin as sun and type in MJ2000Ec.

Figure 5: Coordinate system

3.0.5 Adding New Spacecraft to GMAT

When adding a new spacecraft to [GMAT](#), we are interested only in its orbital properties of it. Under the resource tree, we add new spacecraft. There we are going to see settings regarding [epoch](#) and coordinates. It is important to choose the date as the start of the mission. For coordinates, we choose the coordinate system that we added with Sun origin, and the state type is chosen as Keplerian. On the right part of the tab, we see the elements of the coordinates, that is, [SMA](#), [ECC](#), [INC](#), [RAAN](#), [AOP](#), [TA](#). [GMAT](#) will determine some values but we would like to change those to get to the desired trajectory towards [Mars](#). [19]

Figure 6: Coordinate system

3.0.6 Observing The Simulation Results

In order to verify and test the applied changes in the orbital elements of the spacecraft, we need to have results and frames showing the trajectory of the spacecraft. In order to do that, we right click to “Output” under the resource tree. Then we click “Add” > “OrbitView”. Here we adjust the desired plot options and drawing options. On the right side we select our spacecraft and [Mars](#), [Sun](#), [Phobos](#), and [Deimos](#) as the celestial bodies. The coordinate system is the sun-origin coordinate system that we defined earlier. View Point Reference is “SolarSystemBarycenter”. The view direction is going to be Sun and Axis under the “View Up Definition” is the Z axis.

Figure 7: Coordinate system

These settings will let us see the exact orbit trajectory of the spacecraft as it orbits around Sun. This way we will be able to observe the effects of the changes in the orbital elements of the spacecraft, how the spacecraft behaves with [SRP](#) we defined in the propagator, and lastly, it will help us examine how does it affects the altitude of the spacecraft with [Mars](#). To see the altitude of the spacecraft with [Mars](#) as well as many other properties and output those in a report file, we add “ReportFile”, again after right-clicking output under the resource tree. Here we see the settings for writing the report. On the right side, we decide which parameters to put in the report. In this project, [UTCGregorian](#), [ElapsedSecs](#), [Sun.RMAG](#), [Mars.RMAG](#), [Phobos.RMAG](#), [Deimos.RMAG](#), [ForceModel.Acceleration](#) of apogee and perigee, [Altitude](#), [apogee](#), and [perigee](#) velocities are chosen as parameters. Among these, we are mainly interested in the altitude since we would like to reach [Mars](#) as close as possible and it is the main parameter we observe after making changes in the orbital elements of the spacecraft.

Figure 8: Coordinate system

In terms of examining the results of the adjustments, a report file with these parameters is enough for output. However, it is more convenient to see the spacecraft's point of view for the entire mission. For this purpose, again within output under the resource tree, we add "OpenFrames". This setting creates a frame in which we can monitor the mission in certain settings. The setting we are interested in is the "Object Option". Here we choose our spacecraft in "Selected SC and GS" and for celestial objects we choose Sun, Mars, Deimos, Phobos and we enable "Draw Object", "Draw Trajectory", "Label Body", "Draw Center Maker", "Draw End Markers" to increase the quality of the frame. Lastly, since we want to see the spacecraft's point of view, we make sure to choose the spacecraft to coordinate system under "View Definition". Now as we start the simulation, we can visually see the environment of the spacecraft. This helps with roughly guessing the distance without needing to check the actual values from the report

file, to see if we are on the right track or not.

Figure 9: Open Frames

3.0.7 Defining Mission

Now that all the settings are done, we need to define the mission sequence in order to make the spacecraft run in the specified propagators we created earlier. Defining the mission sequence is relatively simple once we have the propagators. In this project, the Perigee propagator is used initially, after orbiting once, the mission changes itself where it uses perigee and apogee back to back. Keep in mind that “perigee” and “apogee” are just the propagators we defined, they don’t refer to their actual meanings. Since the “apogee” propagator has [SRP](#) on and “perigee” has [SRP](#) off. Although these two are full orbits on their own, when [GMAT](#) is told to use these together, they act like [apogee](#) and [perigee](#).

3.0.8 Effect of SRP in [apogee](#)

Note how we enabled [SRP](#) in [apogee](#) and disabled it in [perigee](#). This setting will cause a force difference between [apogee](#) and [perigee](#). The force acts on the

spacecraft in the opposite direction of the Sun. The force on a flat plate caused by SRP 1AU distance away is defined as:

$$F_{SRP} = PA_e [(\rho_a + \rho_d)\mathbf{s} + \frac{2}{3}\rho_d + 2\rho_s \cos(\alpha)]\mathbf{n} \quad (2)$$

where A_e is the effective area, $\mathbf{s}$ is the sun vector, $\mathbf{n}$ is the sail normal vector, and α is the solar clock angle between the vectors $\mathbf{s}$ and $\mathbf{n}$. [9]

Figure 10: Radiation Pressure Force

[20]

To determine this force's effect in the orbit, at any given moment, we must take the component which is tangent to the orbit, also the component which is perpendicular to the orbit. In these two axes, we calculate the acceleration through the formulas regarding the lightness ratio:

$$a_{SRP} = \frac{2\mu P}{\sigma} \quad (3)$$

$$\beta = \frac{a_{SRP} \times AU^2}{\mu} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma} \quad (5)$$

Where μ is solar gravitational constant ($\mu = 1.3271244004193938 \times 10^{20} \text{ m}^3 / \text{s}^2$). Then we do this calculation for thousands of iterations in **GMAT**. Another thing worth mentioning is that **GMAT** treats the spacecraft as a perfect reflector sphere rather than its actual shape or flat plate unless a SPAD file is used. Although this project aims for a more realistic shape and simulation, for now, we stick with basic calculations. If we wanted to calculate **SRP** on a sphere rather than flat plate, we would need to take the SRP force's tangential and normal components

$$F_n = PA_e [\cos(\alpha \mathbf{n}) - \sin(\alpha \mathbf{t})] \quad (6)$$

$$F_t = PA_e [\cos(\alpha \mathbf{n}) + \sin(\alpha \mathbf{t})] \quad (7)$$

Then add these together

$$F_{SRP} = F_n + F_t = 2PA \cos^2(\alpha) \mathbf{n} = 2PA(\mathbf{s} * \mathbf{n})^2 \mathbf{n} \quad (8)$$

[9]

Figure 11: Photons with angle

Photons on a sphere will pretty much act like a compilation of photons on a flat plate with varying angles. Keep in mind that above calculation is made for a 2D body. For 3D we need to add one more component and then integrate over half sphere. Since light only touches half of the sphere.

Going back to the effect of [SRP](#) force on the orbit, we must do all the above calculations for a considerably high amount of iterations and finally project a realistic orbital trajectory of the spacecraft. Here we trust [GMAT](#)'s perfect sphere assumption since we can assume there is no significant difference between flat

plate and sphere compared to planetary dimensions. That is until SPAD files are implemented in the project. Until then, this project's results will focus on getting into [Mars](#)'s atmosphere and getting as close to the surface as possible. For this purpose, we can let the [GMAT](#) do its calculations with the desired orbital elements.

3.1 Virtual Reality (VR)

Virtual Reality (VR) Utilizing virtual reality to simulate interplanetary voyages provides an unequaled level of immersion and awe-inspiring experience. VR headsets allow users to immerse themselves in faraway celestial bodies, enabling them to explore the surfaces of planets and moons with astonishing realism. Each aspect, from the challenging topography of Mars to the frozen vastness of Europa, is intricately designed using precise scientific information, providing an unparalleled educational encounter. This technology surpasses the constraints of the physical world, enabling individuals to embark on galactic expeditions from the convenience of their own residence. When consumers observe the marvels of the universe, they are motivated by its immense size and attractiveness, sparking a feeling of inquisitiveness and awe that propels the pursuit of space exploration.

Within the vast realm of virtual reality, the aspiration to explore other planets becomes palpably attainable, cultivating a more profound link to the universe and its infinite potential. Due to these factors, the decision was made to employ virtual reality (VR) to mimic the interplanetary voyage to [Mars](#). This is also influenced by the fact that GMAT is compatible with virtual reality headsets. Therefore, the upcoming headlines will pertain to the establishment of the virtual reality system in GMAT.

It should be noted that this setup method mostly pertains to the [Oculus VR](#) headsets, notably the [Oculus Rift S](#) and [Oculus Quest 2](#). While other headsets may function properly, their compatibility has not been verified by the creators of this project. Additionally, the functionality of the VR headgear is significantly influenced by the capabilities of the user's computer. For optimal performance, it is advisable to connect the laptop to a power source when using it. Furthermore, the current version of [GMAT](#), r2022a, does not have the capability to handle virtual reality due to a software glitch. The resolution of this bug and the presence of the bug in future versions are still uncertain. However, the r2020a iteration of [GMAT](#) is fully compatible with virtual reality. Multiple versions can be stored on a computer. However, when incorporating the updated version of the mission into an older version, the user may have to manually delete certain lines in the mission script due to the presence of mistakes. It is important to note that although [GMAT](#) permits 3D virtual reality simulations in the OpenFrames, it does not provide full support for a completely immersive 3D experience where the user can physically be present

within a 360-degree environment, at least in the r2020a version. Nevertheless, the encounter remains in three dimensions, and it is an exceptional occurrence to replicate this Mars expedition within such a setting. Version 3.1.1 Configuring the Oculus device To mimic any mission in GMAT using virtual reality, it is necessary to connect the headset to the computer.

To use [Oculus](#) eyewear, you need to install the [Oculus](#) PC program on your computer. After completing the installation, launch the application. It will prompt you to specify the model of Oculus you are using. Once the selection is made, the setup process will commence. The setup process will differ depending on the specific Oculus model chosen. As an illustration, the Oculus Rift S necessitates the connection of two sensors by USB, whereas the goggles require one HDMI and one USB connection. In the case of the Oculus Quest 2 model, the usage of an Airlink connection eliminates the need for any cable connections. Alternatively, you have the option to attach a USB cable for the headset if desired. This decision may hinge on the availability of sufficient battery power for the Google device. Note that utilizing an Airlink connection necessitates the computer and headset to be linked to the identical WiFi module. Both the Oculus Rift S and the Oculus Quest 2 necessitate the charging of their hand controllers in both scenarios. After completing the requested connections in the Oculus PC program, you can now proceed to establish the boundaries and configure the hand controllers. Utilize the eyewear only when it is deemed essential. On the whole, the setup process for Oculus Rift S appears to be more intricate compared to Oculus Quest 2.

2.3.1.2. Virtual Reality (VR) platform developed by Steam

To mimic any mission in GMAT using virtual reality, it is necessary to connect the headset to the computer. To use Oculus eyewear, you need to install the Oculus PC program on your computer. After completing the installation, launch the application. It will prompt you to specify the model of Oculus you are using. Once the selection is made, the setup process will commence. The setup process will differ depending on the specific Oculus model chosen. As an illustration, the Oculus Rift S necessitates the connection of two sensors by USB, whereas the goggles require one HDMI and one USB connection. For instance, in the case of the Oculus Quest 2 model, utilizing an Airlink connection eliminates the need for any physical cable connections. Alternatively, you have the option to connect a USB cable to the headset. This decision may hinge on the availability of sufficient battery power for the Google device. Note that utilizing an Airlink connection necessitates the computer and headset to be linked to the identical WiFi module. Both the Oculus Rift S and the Oculus Quest 2 necessitate the charging of their hand controllers in both scenarios. After completing the requested connections in the Oculus PC program, you can now proceed to establish the boundaries and configure the hand controllers. Utilize the goggles just when it is essential. On the whole, the setup process for

Oculus Rift S appears to be more intricate compared to that of Oculus Quest 2.

3.1.1 Setting up Oculus

In order to simulate any mission in [GMAT](#) using virtual reality, one must set up their headset on their computer. For [Oculus](#) goggles, this is done by installing the [Oculus](#) PC app on the computer. Once the installation is done, open the app, and it will ask you which model of [Oculus](#) you are using. After choosing that, the setup process will start. Depending on which Oculus model is selected, the setup process will vary. For example, for [Oculus](#) Rift S, will require you to plug in two sensors as USB, and for the goggles, one HDMI and one USB connection will be required. For example [Oculus](#) Quest 2 model, you would not even require a single cable connection if you use an Airlink connection, that is. However, if you wish, you can also connect one USB cable for the headset. This decision may depend on whether the goggle has enough battery or not. Keep in mind that using an Airlink connection would require both the computer and the headset to be connected to the same Wifi module. In both cases, however, both the Oculus Rift S and the Oculus Quest 2 will require both their hand controllers to have their batteries charged up.

Once the connections that the Oculus PC app requests are done, you can now proceed to set up the boundaries and define the hand controllers. Use the goggles when it is necessary. Overall [Oculus](#) Rift S seems to have a more complicated setup process than [Oculus](#) Quest 2.

3.1.2 Steam VR

In order to simulate any mission in [GMAT](#) using virtual reality, one must set up their headset on their computer. For [Oculus](#) goggles, this is done by installing the [Oculus](#) PC app on the computer. Once the installation is done, open the app, and it will ask you which model of Oculus you are using. After choosing that, the setup process will start. Depending on which Oculus model is selected, the setup process will vary. For example, for [Oculus](#) Rift S, will require you to plug in two sensors as USB, and for the goggles, one HDMI and one USB connection will be required. For example [Oculus](#) Quest 2 model, you would not even require a single cable connection if you use an Airlink connection, that is. However, if you wish, you can also connect one USB cable for the headset. This decision may depend on whether the goggle has enough battery or not. Keep in mind that using an Airlink connection would require both the computer and the headset to be connected to the same Wifi module. In both cases, however, both the [Oculus](#) Rift S and the Oculus Quest 2 will require both their hand controllers to have their batteries charged up.

Once the connections that the [Oculus](#) PC app requests are done, you can now proceed to set up the boundaries and define the hand controllers. Use the goggles

when it is necessary. Overall [Oculus](#) Rift S seems to have a more complicated setup process than [Oculus Quest 2](#).

3.2 Discover a Bug In [GMAT](#)

Firstly, I would want to express my gratitude to Dr. Pinto for reaching out to the developers of the [GMAT](#). The acronym "GMAT" stands for Graduate Management Admission Test. The information regarding the Martian atmosphere is limited. Obtained from NASA. A request was made to use NASA's MARS-GRAM (Mars Global Reference Atmospheric Model) program, but no response was received. Upon realizing the program's incompatibility, we promptly initiated a search for an alternative option. Prior to seeking an alternative solution, it was necessary for us to verify the validity of the tests. Therefore, we conducted a basic simulation to ascertain the presence of an environment. Surrounding [Mars](#). Hence, a rudimentary script was devised that can be easily prepared by anyone. In this simulation, the outcome of introducing an atmosphere to [Mars](#) was found to be identical to the outcome of not introducing an atmosphere to [Mars](#). It has been conclusively demonstrated that the Martian atmosphere is either not located where it is expected to be or is absent altogether.

Using Atmosphere plots:

Figure 12 shows the propagator settings. Mars Atmosphere model is located as Exponential.

Figure 12: Propagator Settings for with Exponential Atmosphere

Figure 13: With Martian Atmosphere

This figure shows Solar Sail orbiting around Mars without being affected by any force. There is no change in [perigee](#) and [apogee](#) values.

Figure 14: Solar Sail's altitude with respect to Mars

As can be seen in the plot, no change was recorded in the altitude value. From this we can conclude that there is no atmosphere around Mars.

Without Atmosphere Plot:

This figure shows the propagator settings. The Mars Atmosphere model was chosen as None to see if there is a difference. However, no change was observed.

Figure 15: Propagator Settings for without atmosphere try

This figure shows the altitude of the Solar Sail with respect to Mars. The values in this figure are the same as in the plot with the atmosphere option. This proves once again that there is no atmosphere on the GMAT.

Figure 16: Solar Sail’s altitude with respect to Mars

This time Dr. Pinto contacted [Darrel Conway](#). Darrel gave a script to be used in the [GMAT](#) program. When this script was added and simulated, no difference was observed. Then a simple script was used to see if there was any atmosphere around [Mars](#) and no atmosphere was found after this simulation. Thus, it was discovered that the Martian atmosphere was not in the right place on the GMAT. Darrel was then contacted again and this was explained to him. Darrel said that we found a BUG in the program. After some time Darrel sent a zip file by email and explained step by step what to do. This file contained the Atmospheric values of Mars. After unzipping the zip file as Darrel said and placing it where he said, a test was done and it was observed that the Martian atmosphere was present. In the following simulations we successfully performed the [Aerobraking](#) maneuver thanks to the Martian atmosphere, which we will describe in the [3.3](#) section on the following pages.

3.3 Aerobraking in [GMAT](#)

Achieving interplanetary travel to [Mars](#) solely with solar radiation pressure is an inherently difficult endeavor. However, the primary goal of this project is not only to achieve the task of reaching [Mars](#), but also to successfully get into orbit around it. Alternatively, if not addressed, the ship will be lost in the vastness of outer space. As mentioned before, one method to accomplish this is by use air drag to decelerate the spacecraft.

Once a functional atmospheric model is obtained in [GMAT](#), the spacecraft’s tra-

jectory is modified to utilize just the necessary amount of atmospheric drag in order to achieve the target orbit. Simulating successful aerobraking has encountered numerous obstacles. The first aspect pertains to the atmospheric model of Mars utilized in the simulation. The atmospheric gas density generally decreases as height increases. In addition, the rate at which gas density decreases has a falling pattern as altitude increases. The data provided is extracted from the text file containing information on the atmosphere in the simulation. The values are as follows:

Table 1: Altitude vs Density table

Altitude(km)	Density (kg/m³)
0	0,012003017
20	0,002106355
40	0,000226873
60	1,53E-05
80	9,81E-07
100	5,31E-08
120	3,25E-09
140	4,13E-10
160	8,12E-11
180	1,84E-11
200	4,60E-12
220	1,40E-12
240	5,28E-13
260	2,37E-13
280	1,19E-13
300	6,44E-14
320	3,67E-14
340	2,18E-14
360	1,35E-14

The initial column represents the height measured in kilometers, while the sub-

sequent column represents the density measured in kilograms per cubic meter. Based on the statistics, it is evident that the variation in density is significantly larger for lower altitudes compared to higher altitudes. This suggests that unless the spacecraft is in close proximity to the surface, it will not experience any significant effects even if it enters the atmosphere. It is important to mention that beyond a specific height, the atmosphere gets significantly less dense. This leads to computational challenges in the simulation as the computer is handling extremely minuscule values. Consequently, it was postulated that there is an absence of atmosphere beyond a specific altitude. This assumption significantly simplifies the simulation with few errors. An further obstacle in aerobraking is the true achievement of orbit rather than merely altering the spacecraft's trajectory slightly, only to subsequently be lost in the depths of space once more. Alternatively, redirecting it to such an extent that the spacecraft collides with Mars during its initial or subsequent orbits. Attaining the optimal level of aerodynamic drag is crucial, particularly given the delicate variations in density. In the previous simulation, spacecraft without the atmospheric model were able to reach a maximum altitude of approximately 40 meters above the Earth. With the given atmospheric model, this trajectory will inevitably lead to a collision with the surface even before completing a single orbit. The following figures depict the deviation in trajectory as a function of varying minimum altitude values.

Figure 17: 60.3832 km

Figure 18: 60.3991 km

Figure 19: 60.4063 km

As seen from images, even with the altitude differences of between 10 and 20 meters, the trajectory of the spacecraft changes significantly. The third case may seem large enough to get into a successful orbit. However all three of these cases ended up as spacecraft crashing into the planet. This is another challenge of the process. In order to overcome this challenge, solar radiation pressure is used. Firstly, orbital elements of the spacecraft has been adjusted so that it approaches Mars from the day side instead of night side. This step plays crucial role for using radiation pressure after first deflection. When the spacecraft approaches Mars from day side, the angle of sun lights will help spacecraft to push its orbit slightly, making it avoid the crash and survive for at least one more loop. The position of sun can be seen in the above images. In the simulation, spacecraft has enabled the solar radiation pressure after reaching 61 km of altitude. This resulted as change in the orbiting trajectory. In the images, trajectory after 61 km altitude is indicated as the blue color. The above images are trajectories without solar radiation pressure, and the following three images are the trajectories which includes solar radiation pressure in the blue trajectory, respectively.

Figure 20: 60.3832 km with SRP

Figure 21: 60.3991 km with SRP

Figure 22: 60.4063 km with SRP

Images shows that for the first two cases, the spacecraft still crashes into **Mars**. However, with the help of solar radiation pressure, longer orbiting trajectory, and correct sunlight angle, the spacecraft in the third case was able to survive and successfully orbited **Mars**. Keep in mind that the reason there is slight change in the orbit in each loop is because the solar radiation pressure is always enabled. A more realistic approach would be turning **SRP** off once the spacecraft orbit reaches a desired **apogee** and **perigee**, that is, far away from **Mars** just enough to stay safe from atmospheric effects. For this purpose, another simulation has been made.

Figure 23: Trajectory around Mars

In this simulation, the yellow trajectory has **SRP** enabled, red and white trajectory has it disabled. This green and red trajectories are based on the Sun's **perigee** and **apogee**. That is the reason their positions are changing for each loop. The Sun's position is changing. White trajectory starts after 10 loops of green and red loop. The increase in the **perigee** can be seen clearly.

Figure 24: Closer view

The [perigee](#) and [apogee](#) altitude values for each loop is shown below. This method makes use of enabling and disabling SRP allows spacecraft to not get close to a dangerous zone. Based on the atmosphere model in [GMAT](#), there is no effect of atmosphere after 2980km of altitude. This method moved spacecraft's [perigee](#) above 3000km of altitude, which can be considered safe.

Table 2: Periapsis(km) vs Apoapsis(km)

Periapsis (km)	Apoapsis (km)
3051,480195	99158,25635
2694,464967	99157,41695
2354,094561	99005,74365
2030,649749	98834,58353
1725,002486	98604,85114
1435,845654	98352,69498
1164,571531	98037,43227
910,645462	97710,75034
673,056354	97319,83212
452,040881	96889,75292
247,441477	96444,27411
60,406175	95992,62028

4 Results and Discussion

In this figure (Figure 25), we can see our Solar Sail's trajectory. It can be easily noticed, it was observed that the [apogee](#) value increased after each period. Semi Major Axis([SMA](#)) is set to 101919900.6120019km. After 207400281, 146319seconds [solar-sail](#) reaches the minimum altitude for [Mars](#).

Figure 25: Orbit View

Our initial conditions are shown in the figure below:

Figure 26: Initial Conditions

We took this figure from [GMAT](#). This figure (Figure27) shows us [solar-sail](#) is approaching Mars.

Figure 27: Mars view

This figure (Figure 28) shows us that our [solar-sail](#) passed without hitting [Mars](#).

Figure 28: Mars view 2

After that, we change the parameters for aiming Aerobraking in the [Mars](#) Atmosphere. But unfortunately [GMAT](#), doesn't have an sufficient atmosphere for [Mars](#).

Our parameters for [solar-sail](#) were shown in the below:

Figure 29: Our Parameters

As can be seen in this table, Semi-Major Axix (**SMA**) is decreasing by 10 kilometers per line. The left side of the table is **SMA** difference between the initial condition and our conditions. The middle part of the table is Altitude from **Mars** to **solar-sail**. As the **SMA** difference increases, the altitude value between the **solar-sail** and the **Mars** decreases. The right side of the table contains Elapsed seconds in this mission. Total Elapsed Seconds are approximately 6.5 years. As aerobraking discussed in the 1.3 and 1.3.1

Table 3: **Without Atmosphere of Mars**

SMA Difference	Altitude (km)	Elapsed Sec (s)
0	5,52E+03	207400260,355800
10	4,97E+03	207400260,559388
20	4,40E+03	207400254,41847
30	3,82E+03	207400265,802945
40	3,25E+03	207400267,063975
50	2,68E+03	207400268,765402
60	2,12E+03	207400272,401995
70	1,57E+03	207400274,994881
80	1,03E+03	207400277,162944
90	5,05E+02	207400279,1156910
100	0.04598306789966955	207400281,146319

Elapsed Seconds vs Mars Altitude plot: The spacecraft's altitude graph is seen here. The number of seconds the spacecraft has been in orbit is shown on the Y-Axis. The spacecraft's altitude from Mars, expressed in kilometers, is shown by the X-Axis.

Figure 30: Elapsed Sec-Mars Altitude

Elapsed Second vs Sun Altitude plot: The spacecraft's altitude to the Sun graph is shown below. In the Y-Axis it represents a number of seconds the spacecraft has been in orbit. X-Axis represents to altitude value of the spacecraft to the Sun. As we can see in the graph after each period distance is increasing so the **apogee** value is increasing.

Figure 31: Elapsed Sec-Sun Altitude

Elapsed Days vs VMAG of the Spacecraft plot: This plot has shown us Spacecraft's velocity increases after each [apogee](#) period. The decrease in the plot means Spacecraft is in the [perigee](#) period. As it moves further away from the sun in each period, the velocity difference increases in each period. The elapsed seconds are shown on the X-Axis. In the Y-Axis, the velocity magnitude is shown.

Figure 32: Elapsed Sec-Velocity Magnitude

4.1 Proof of Concept

In this part of our report, we will show you that our concept is indeed possible. the plots we put below are from the [Jupyter Notebook](#). In these plots, we have respectively [RMAG](#), Velocity, the top view of the solar sail as it passes around the moons, and the trajectory of the solar sail after it passes around [Mars](#).

In contrast to the simulation, these plots show that the velocity of the solar sail is reduced by the Martian atmosphere and its trajectory changes. The reason why the orbit change is not visible in the [GMAT](#) simulation is that the atmosphere of [Mars](#) is not fully reflected in [GMAT](#). With applications such as Mars-Gram, the orbit change can be seen much more clearly.

Also, a more realistic simulation can be prepared with SPAD files.

[RMAG](#) vs Elapsed Seconds plot: The plot below shows the [RMAG](#) value and the elapsed seconds. As can be seen, after a certain point, the [RMAG](#) value decreased suddenly. After the sudden drop, it showed a decreasing and increasing graph. This shows us that the solar sail has settled into the orbit of the [Mars](#).

[21]

Figure 33: Jupyter Notebook RMAG

Velocity of The [solar-sail](#) vs Elapsed Seconds plot: This plot shows the Speed and Elapsed Seconds graph of our [solar-sail](#). In this graph, the sudden drop in our velocity value shows us that we are being [Aerobraking](#) by [Mars](#). It shows a decreasing value from the sudden drop and then we can see that it slowly accelerates again. [21]

Figure 34: Jupyter Notebook Velocity Plot

This graph above shows our trajectory during [Aerobraking](#). The top view of the graph makes it easier to observe the change of the trajectory. The curve around [Mars](#) shows us that the orbit changes with [Aerobraking](#).

Figure 35: Jupyter Notebook Upper View

[21]

The bottom graph shows us our trajectory. It shows that we have a new orbit around Mars after being Aerobraking by the Martian atmosphere. This graph is the clearest graph that shows us briefly that our project is possible. Of course, it is possible to make it even more realistic, but since we do not have access to the Mars-Gram files and GMAT does not have a sufficient atmosphere of Mars, it is normal that the simulation and Jupyter Notebook plots show different values.

Figure 36: Jupyter Notebook Trajectory

[21]

5 Conclusion

This research article utilizes solar sailing as a propulsion method for spacecraft, employing the free open-source NASA [GMAT](#) software. The primary aim of the study is to examine the fuel efficiency and sustained acceleration of this methodology. The text highlights the benefits of utilizing solar energy for space travel compared to traditional spacecraft. It particularly stresses the advantages in terms of cost, accessibility, and decreased fuel usage. The objective is to prove the viability of using solar energy for interplanetary missions, namely those directed towards [Mars](#). The presented research outlines a comprehensive methodology for simulating and analyzing the orbital design and flight dynamics of a practical solar-powered spacecraft of the CubeSat class. The objective is to target orbits around [Mars](#) and its moons, [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#). The simulation model also incorporates the integration of these moons into the analysis, along with immersive simulations. Virtual reality ([VR](#)) technology was utilized.

Through the implementation of simulations and extensive study, a multitude of objectives were successfully accomplished. Firstly, the addition of Mars' moons [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#) in the scenario distinguished this project as one of the few projects incorporated in [GMAT](#). Unlike the previous project,[\[3\]](#), which descended around 60.4 km in the Martian atmosphere using CubeSat [Aerobraking](#), this project successfully decelerated and landed. This objective was crucial for examining and illustrating the orbital behavior of the spacecraft propelled by solar sails. The computer subsequently generated a visual representation of the transit orbits of Mars' moons, [Phobos](#) and [Deimos](#). This application aims to enhance the realism of spacecraft mission design by simulating orbit and flight dynamics. In addition, graphs illustrating the distances and changes in orbital vehicle positions over time were plotted based on the [SMA](#), [ECC](#), [TA](#), [AOP](#), [INC](#), and [RAAN](#) orbital parameters. The Horizons System utilized the data to forecast orbital parameters based on the duration of the mission. The projected elements were utilized to ascertain the precise location of each spacecraft at the moment of impact, a crucial factor in the collision avoidance study. The significance of collision avoidance was to illustrate that the spacecraft's trajectory could be disturbed by another spacecraft or a celestial object, such as the moons of [Mars](#), which could have a substantial influence on the spacecraft's orbit. It was mutually decided that if there was a potential collision with another spacecraft, a little adjustment would be made to the spaceship's sails in order to avert the accident. This study employed plotting techniques to visually demonstrate the significance of the variation in the reflection coefficient based on the instantaneous speed and distance from the sun. The [GMAT](#) has demonstrated that the maximal instantaneous speed rises in tandem with an increase in the reflection coefficient. Furthermore, a glitch pertaining to

the depiction of the Martian atmosphere was identified in the NASA [GMAT](#). The appropriate channels were promptly notified, and a valuable contribution was made towards its improvement.

This article examines the application of solar sailing as a method of propelling spacecraft, with a specific emphasis on optimizing fuel consumption and maintaining a continuous acceleration. The text provides a comprehensive examination of the discoveries and benefits of solar sailing, emphasizing its potential for incorporation into orbital and [Mars](#) orbital missions. It also explores the creation of a dependable simulation model and the utilization of supplementary software packages for analysis and simulations. This study delves into the difficulties of effectively replicating aerobraking, specifically focusing on the declining gas density as altitude increases in the Martian atmosphere and the necessity of attaining the optimal level of aerodynamic drag to prevent collisions with Mars. In the future, [GMAT](#) may incorporate additional orbiters around [Mars](#) and other celestial bodies in the Solar System to enhance the accuracy and realism of the mission. The current project's objective is to guarantee the safe landing of [solar-sail](#) on Mars. [GMAT](#) can be enhanced by incorporating small asteroids and orbital debris with orbiters, leading to a substantial enhancement in mission quality.

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